

“AS AN OF EDUCATING ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE SPIRIT OF FRIENDSHIP AND HUMANITY IN FOLK PEDAGOGY”

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Annotation: In this article, it is mentioned about the importance of paying special attention to the educational process of primary grade students in the people's pedagogy, nurturing them in terms of friendship and humanity.

Key words: Folk pedagogy, oral tradition of the people, education, lesson, friendship, humanity, upbringing, sayings, attention, future generations. The role of the people's pedagogy in nurturing primary grade students in the spirit of friendship and humanity is of great importance. People's pedagogy did not develop overnight during the era of independence; over the years, it has evolved from generation to generation, becoming a national upbringing model that serves as a means of education and upbringing for students in the spirit of humanity and patriotism.

"Regular engagement in developing children's thinking abilities and their upbringing is crucial. Indeed, it is a sacred duty entrusted to the teacher's attention and conscience. The power, beauty, and breadth of noble thoughts are dependent on the teacher's upbringing." [1:14]. At the same time, the author emphasizes the interconnectedness of education and upbringing: "Although there may be some differences between teaching and upbringing, they are inseparable, one's existence is like soul to body for the other" [1:15]. In other words, our great ancestor Abdulla Avloniy, who contributed significantly to the development of national pedagogy and oral literature, focused his attention on the upbringing of children to become complete individuals. By paying attention to each element for the child's growth from an educational and moral perspective, if the child is engaged regularly, it is possible to achieve accurate and correct results. This also highlights the teacher's skill in paying attention to the students' upbringing level based on their attention, intellect, and conscience, emphasizing the great responsibility placed on the teacher's insight and proving that a child's upbringing is dependent on the teacher's guidance. It also underscores the importance of consistency in engaging with children in education and upbringing, as well as emphasizing that each word in education and upbringing plays a crucial role in a child's development. It also stresses that a child's maturity depends on all these elements and that achieving the desired

goal through both education and upbringing is essential, as only through both can a child's development in upbringing be envisioned, not just a child's upbringing being disrupted, thus reaching the intended goal through both."

"The powerful influence, importance, and vitality of the national pedagogy lie in the fact that 'firstly, if its existence, influence, depth, and meaning are present in the life of an individual, secondly, it is created in living traditions by the people, seeking solutions to life and human issues, and thirdly, it is aimed at general human values and universal human ideals.' Throughout their activities, each teacher utilizes examples of national pedagogy in nurturing students. The manifestation of the level of development of national pedagogy is evidenced by its formation based on life events, the significance of its meaning in child upbringing, the reflection of our national traditions, and the search for solutions to issues that occur in life, forming the essence of universal human values in child upbringing. The transition from oral transmission to written form by the people and being passed down through generations as a spiritual heritage to our future generations indicates the progressive nature of national pedagogy.

The proverbs used in Uzbek national pedagogy serve to shape feelings of respect, friendship, and humanity in students. For example:

"An elder brother is like a father."

"If the father is pleased, then God is pleased."

"A friend who counts is not a friend. A friend who is counted on is irreplaceable."

From the above proverbs, it can be understood that starting from when a child goes to school, they begin writing with the help of a teacher, learning to read, and gradually understanding the world. Why does a friend matter? What is humanity itself? These are questions that will be addressed through practical teaching processes, such as asking the student why they need a computer in a technology lesson. If the student doesn't know what to do, they are advised to seek help from their friends (classmates). If that friend can provide assistance when needed, then they will become closer friends, and the student will start turning to their classmates for their own benefit. In this case, the student asks for help from that classmate. Based on this, they understand that friendship is necessary for mutual assistance and for sharing their own issues. The concept of humanity begins with compassion and love, the need to lend a helping hand to others as much as possible, and through this, it continues in fostering kindness. The success of students also depends on the great role of the teacher. Along with providing education, the teacher also contributes their own feelings to the

child's upbringing process, ensuring that the best qualities of correctness and humanity are instilled."

"The fact that each child's first encounter with toys, objects, and games that they can learn through in their surroundings plays a significant role in their moral upbringing is evident. Toys become imprinted on the child's imagination like a seal on clay, staying with them for a lifetime. The choices a child makes, the path they will take in the future, how they will shape their lifestyle based on ethical and moral principles, and especially how they interact with other children during their childhood are all indicated by the toys they play with.

In traditional folk pedagogy, attention has always been paid to the toys children play with during their childhood to shape virtues of friendship and humanity. Indeed, it has been mentioned that some toys have been used to predict which profession a child will pursue in the future based on the toys they play with. Toys may seem simple at first glance, but they hold a significant place in a child's life because playing with toys helps to cultivate qualities of friendship, kindness, and humanity within them and allows them to start exploring their own imagination.

The importance of oral creativity in folk pedagogy, particularly the significance of stories and fables, in influencing children's upbringing process is crucial. "In stories, patriotism, hard work, humanity, courage, justice, mercy, love, nobility, loyalty, and friendship are expressed. It is worth paying attention to the content of some stories." In this context, we can cite the following proverbs mentioned by J. Junaydullayev in his book "Folk Pedagogy" as examples:

- A fortunate person has luck, a hardworking person has a crown.
- A friend to a knowledgeable person is a companion.
- United rivers become a sea; separated trees become firewood.

Proverbs help shape children's noble human feelings and patriotic sentiments, organizing their relationship with the environment and people around them in an orderly manner. For example:

A friend helps a friend,

Water helps grass grow.

A friend does not abandon a stone thrown.

Follow your friend's footsteps; you will reach your destination.

A friend is generous; an enemy is deceitful.

A friend is known in difficult times.

A true friend keeps his secret from enemies.

Don't kick the ladder of a friend climbing up.

The concept of friendship is considered noble and sacred for elementary school students. Because the notion of friendship instills feelings of love, compassion, and loyalty in children, proverbs help students better understand the bonds of friendship.

Folk tales such as "Zumrad and Qimmat," "The Golden Watermelon," "The Farmer and the Bear," "Bread and Gold" (Arab folk tale), "Haqqush" (Tajik folk tale), "Danak" (Kyrgyz folk tale), "Qizg'anchiq Pak" (Korean folk tale), "Strength and Weakness" (Latvian folk tale), "The Seventh Son," "The Wolf and the Lamb," and similar tales are stories that young children enjoy reading and exploring with fascination. The spiritual legacy of folk pedagogy aims to elevate children's spiritual values, broaden their horizons, help them develop into intelligent, honest, hardworking individuals with compassionate hearts, and shape positive qualities while avoiding negative habits.

In conclusion, it can be said that folk pedagogy and examples of oral creativity play a crucial role in shaping elementary school students into mature individuals from a young age by nurturing them in terms of friendship, humanity, and patriotism. They also serve as essential tools in instilling feelings of friendship and fostering a spirit of loyalty among students."

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